

Advantage of using authentic materials and innovative methods in practice in learning english

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o`rganishda autentik til materiallarini to`g`ri qo`llash, moslashtirish muammolarini o`rganish va innovatsion metodlardan foydalanish keltirilgan.

**Kalit so`zlar:** til, autentik material, til ko`nikmalari, texnologiyalar, tahlil, amaliy dars.

Annotation. In this article, it is given the correct use of authentic language materials, the study of adaptation problems and the use of innovative methods in learning English.

Keywords: language, authentic material, language skills, technologies, analysis, practical lesson.

Абстрактный. В данной статье представлено правильное использование аутентичных языковых материалов, изучение проблем адаптации и использование инновационных методов в изучении английского языка.

Ключевые слова: язык, аутентичный материал, языковые навыки, технологии, анализ, практическое занятие.

Today, the world community is experiencing a process of high globalization. Use of media-information bases; relations based on scientific, socio-economic, exchange of experience; study, improve skills, work abroad; international tourism naturally reflects globalization. These processes increase our demand and need for additional language learning. The desire of young people to learn foreign languages, especially one of the international languages, is increasing.

In our age, which is developing day by day, it is possible to observe that in the process of language learning, along with some effective methods, resources, some problems are also encountered. These include not knowing where to start language learning, lack of initial knowledge for independent learning, lack of resources and materials, or inability to use them independently. It should be noted that the use of

authentic materials during practical lessons in learning a foreign language helps to effectively solve these problems. At this point, it is necessary to pay special attention to the use of "real materials" in learning a foreign language. "Authentic materials provide real-life examples of language used in everyday situations. They can be used to further increase the interest of students."

Authentic materials, whether they focus on reading or listening comprehension skills, are actually informational and not intended for language teaching learning purposes. They can include films, plays, works of art, scientific texts, newspapers and magazines, and television shows. Non-authentic materials include audio and video clips invented, written or recorded for learning a particular language. They include textbooks, manuals, or materials designed in imitation of real materials for language learners, specifically aimed at language learning. Of course, the use of these materials makes the work of teachers much easier. Authentic materials help to enrich the teaching process and increase students' interest in language learning. If the authentic materials are selected according to the educational programs presented in the textbooks, there will be no problems in the process of searching and selecting them, only then these materials will have coherence and a logical sequence. When authentic materials are developed and made available to the public, it is assumed that the consumer can understand the language used at the level of their native language, and no language is specialized for learners, that is, without some special language learning or teaching structures. Its advantages are exactly that. That is, while using these materials, the language learner will encounter expressions, slangs, accents, academic words used by natives in real life language, even dialects, and in general aspects of real language. Real materials allow you to get acquainted with the original features of the language.

The main stage of teaching a foreign language in universities teaching linguistics and other languages is to determine the ways to achieve its goals. This goal combines the following methods from the point of view of teaching foreign languages; sections of linguistics (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar) and language skills (reading, speaking, listening, writing). Teaching these aspects involves different teaching methods and is a separate topic for discussion. Special attention is paid to linguistic competence as a basis in foreign language methodology.

Innovative technologies in the field of education are constantly developing, their types are expanding. The following main groups of technologies can be distinguished:

1. Information and communication technologies in the field of studying the subject or ICT. The use of these technologies is the development of the information society and it is related to the active introduction of information media in all spheres of life. Such technologies are aimed at informing students' minds. Educational programs owns new sciences aimed at learning informatics, information processes and ICT includes To increase the information culture of professors and students the educational process is also being actively informed to help.

2. Person-oriented technologies. These technologies are personal training and aimed at putting it in a priority place in education. The entire educational process the person, taking into account the individuality and development characteristics of the person aimed at development.

3. Providing information and analysis of the educational process. From this group of technologies use the development of each student, class, parallel, educational institution focused on research and their adequate assessment.

4. Monitoring of intellectual development. Technologies from graphics based on use, test system, new evaluation methods, they the dynamics of individual students' development and the quality of education in general allows tracking.

5. Educational technologies. The educational process cannot be separated from education.

6. Didactic technologies. They are the main factor in the development of the educational institution is considered Such technologies are traditional and innovative technologies is based on a set of techniques and tools that include the use of: training independent work with literature, audiovisual, multimedia, classified use of teaching methods.his, new ways of developing a person and his main qualities are current being done.

One of the main requirements for personnel today is excellent knowledge of foreign languages. It is appropriate to rely on the directions of modern linguistics in teaching a foreign language. This is taken into account in the new foreign language program. For this purpose, the teacher approaches the students from the point of view of practical mastering of the material. Therefore, the work of students is aimed at effective (speech, written expression) and receptive (listening, reading) acquisition of language materials, expanding the potential vocabulary of students. The basis of solid education is the effective generalization and improvement of the teaching process.

Recently, optimization is also widely used. Optimization is the ability to search for and select and apply an easy, convenient method, method, method, system, principle, tool, exercise that is suitable for students of higher education institutions with a foreign language and their chosen directions, conditions, conditions. being taught. Optimization is specific for different types of higher education institutions, because the teaching hours are different and also have different effects on the characteristics of the students' native language. The current period requires the development of communicative competence, giving information (speaking, expressing thoughts in writing) and receiving information (through reading, listening and understanding) in a foreign language.

In conclusion, it should be noted that Information and communication technologies it has become commonplace in kindergartens, schools, academies, and universities. The rapid development of society, the technologies and methods of the educational process demands the need to change. Graduates of educational institutions should be ready for changing modern trends. Therefore, in education focused on individual approach, mobility and remoteness the introduction of technologies seems necessary and inevitable. In order to make language learning productive and interesting, as well as to enrich it, it is possible to achieve the desired results if, instead of limiting yourself to textbooks, you prepare educational materials from authentic materials and take a deeper approach to education.

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